

MEM[]RIAV

Documentation and preservation guide for video game creators

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1. Introduction

1.1 Who is it for?

Creating video games takes time and resources. This guide is therefore intended as a quick reference for anyone interested in learning the first simple reflexes for documenting their work, the results of that work, and the administrative and financial activities involved in game production.

This best practice guide is intended for:

- **any member of a video game development studio,**
- **anyone involved in the creation of video games.**

Designed specifically for Switzerland, this guide can be adapted and applied to other production contexts. This guide is intended to be updated over time.

1.2 Why?

Video games are a major and recognized cultural practice, and are beginning to take their place within various cultural institutions. The missions of these institutions are to preserve, document and make available cultural heritage. No value judgement is involved, as all cultural production is of heritage interest.

However, as a number of studies, such as the Pixelvetica project¹, have shown, video games are a complex medium, requiring specific processes to ensure their preservation at all levels.

Good documentation practices are also useful for studios and designers. Properly documenting your creations allows you to:

- **create a database of documentation** and internal resources from the various projects, useful for future productions, communication and promotion of the work carried out,
- **enhance the long-term value of one's work**, by depositing one's creations in cultural institutions so that they become part of the collective memory,
- **limit data storage costs**, while enabling documents to be retrieved years later if they have been deposited in an institution.

This guide addresses the issues of documentation and archiving.

- The aim of game *documentation* by designers is to **gather all the information essential to the memory and understanding of** a project.

¹See <https://rapport.pixelvetica.ch>

- The aim of archiving is to **preserve and ensure the long-term readability** of the game and its documents. It is carried out by professionals (cultural institutions, consultants).

Depositing for archiving purposes does not mean "granting public access", still less "release"! Strict conditions of access apply in accordance with archiving regulations. They can also be regulated on a case-by-case basis at the time of deposit by means of an agreement signed by both parties. The usual copyrights apply.

This guide is accompanied by sample forms to help you document the essential information involved in producing a video game.

1.3 How to use this guide

This guide aims to provide practical resources to help designers document their work.

- The recommendations in this guide do not necessarily have to be followed in their entirety when documenting your work. Every step counts, especially as time and resources are limited. We therefore invite you to pick and choose what is most relevant to your situation, and to make these resources your own.
- Each section can be dealt with separately. They contain both a summary of essential information, and detailed explanations - with the exception of section 3.4, which is dedicated to a short presentation of useful tools.
- The appendices include useful resources for implementing solutions quickly.
- A glossary accompanies this guide to define certain terms. Defined terms are underlined in the text.

2. Video game documentation

2.1 History of the studio, history of games created

In brief

- **Each studio and independent creator is invited to compile and maintain an up-to-date history of its activities and members, wherever possible.**
- **A simple summary document can say a lot. Two sample tables are included with this guide. We recommend that you include comprehensive credits for each game.**

More details

Each studio and independent creator is invited to compile and maintain an up-to-date history of its activities and members, wherever possible.

This information makes it possible to date the studio's productions more accurately. This information is invaluable to archivists, especially when the studio is no longer in business. In such cases, the archiving process becomes crucial, given the risk of loss, compared with that of a studio still in business.

We recommend being sensitive to the instability of oral and undocumented information, which risks being lost if not written down. Know-how held by a specific person within a specific studio or project is also at risk in the event of departure.

A simple summary document can say a lot. Two sample tables are included with this guide. We recommend that you include comprehensive credits for each game.

2.2 What to document

In brief

- Useful documents to keep are:
 - For the game:
 - The game's source code,
 - Visual and sound assets,
 - Game design documents,
 - Narrative design documents,
 - Any "physical" documents (game box, merchandising, etc.)
 - For the context of the game:
 - Administrative, project management and human resources documents,
 - Contracts,
 - Financial documents,
 - Promotional documents (marketing and communication).
- In particular, we recommend documenting:
 - Software tools used,
 - Versions of all tools and software used,
 - All product element formats,
 - Intermediate versions of code and visual and audio assets

More details

The documents required to create a game bring together the fundamental information needed to preserve these video games in the best possible conditions, as they provide information on several essential aspects:

- The context and creation process of the game in question,
- Financing and administrative organization of production,
- Versions of software and tools used by developers and artists (visuals, sounds, music)
- The different versions of the game and the assets created by them,

- All these documents should ideally be:
 - Documented and preserved by the creators so that they can be easily reused for future productions,
 - Deposited for archiving in a cultural institution when these documents are no longer of use to them.

Useful documents to keep are:

- For the game :
 - The game's source code,
 - Visual and sound assets,
 - Game design documents,
 - Narrative design documents,
 - Any "physical" documents (game box, merchandising, etc.)
- For the context of the game:
 - Administrative, project management and human resources documents,
 - Contracts,
 - Financial documents,
 - Promotional documents (marketing and communication).

As keeping all these elements is demanding in terms of time and resources, we recommend concentrating efforts on the documents relating to the game, and on all the documents regulating everyone's rights to the game (author, distribution, reuse, etc.).

In particular, we recommend documenting:

- Software tools used,
- Versions of all tools and software used,
- All product elements formats,
- Intermediate versions of code and visual and audio assets.

We are well aware that it is extremely difficult to document all the changes and versions of a game (which often continue after its release). However, any versioning or short documents indicating major changes are welcome (e.g. internal or public release notes, major changes in art direction or game design).

2.3 How to document?

In brief

- We recommend the use of free, archiving-compatible software, tools and formats.

More details

We recommend that, wherever possible, designers use document formats that are compatible with archiving, to guarantee lasting access to information. For example²:

- CSV (.csv),
- text (.txt),
- markdown (.md),

We recommend being careful about using proprietary tools, software and formats that do not allow:

- Easy access to service over the long term,
- Easy reuse of files,
- Work stability, as each company can change its conditions of use from one day to the next (e.g. Unity).

We therefore recommend the use of free software, tools and formats that guarantee long-term access, or minimize the risk of losing access to files.

There are various ways of documenting the production of the game, its reception or the game itself:

- Screenshots or videos of gameplay, or of getting to grips with the game,
- Text describing the game mechanics,
- "Bible" containing information on the universe, characters, etc.
- Photograph or video of public presentations of the game,
- Mention of the game in the press or on the Internet.

²The Library of Congress maintains an annual list of recommended formats for preserving digital objects <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/TOC.html>

2.4 Rights management

In brief

- We recommend that studios and designers:
 - Ensure that they remain the owners of the rights to their works, or at least that they know precisely the identity of all persons (legal or physical) who hold the rights.
 - Ensure that there are no restrictions on the distribution, use and communication of the game, or elements of the game.
- Request a special agreement, allowing the game and its documents to be deposited with a cultural institution for archiving.

More details

We strongly recommend that every creator or studio ask themselves who owns the rights, and which rights, to their game. Indeed, rights management is an essential element in the game's promotion and archiving processes. For example, it may be forbidden to distribute concept art produced for a game without explicit authorization, or to show the results of your work on one's website.

We therefore recommend that studios and designers:

- Ensure that they remain the owners of the rights to their works, or at least that they know precisely the identity of all persons (legal or physical) who hold the rights.
- Ensure that there are no restrictions on the distribution, use and communication of the game, or elements of the game.
- Request a special agreement, allowing the game and its documents to be deposited with a cultural institution for archiving.

3. Archiving a video game

3.1 Indicate the existence of your game

In brief

- **Once a video game has been released, we recommend reporting it to various databases and platforms, which do their utmost to list Swiss video games.**

More details

Once a video game has been released, we recommend reporting it to various databases and platforms, which do their utmost to list Swiss video games. This would make it easier to identify and preserve the information essential to understanding the project. For example:

- **[Swiss Games Garden](#)**
A database of Swiss video game production, designed to preserve and promote its memory. It is a collaborative platform maintained by the GameLab Lausanne³ video game study group, documenting over 800 Swiss games (with their metadata). The aim of this database is to list the entire Swiss video game production.
- **["Video games in Switzerland"](#) (Wikipedia)**
Wikipedia page devoted to video games in Switzerland, detailing history, industry, associations, research and exhibitions.
- **["Video game developed in Switzerland"](#) (Wikipedia)**
Wikipedia page listing all video games developed in Switzerland (page to be updated and completed).
- **[Swiss Games Showcase username](#) (Wikidata)**
Add a specific identifier in Wikidata to categorize it as a Swiss video game.

³See <https://gamelab-lausanne.ch/>

3.2 Submitting a video game for archiving

In brief

- We recommend handing over the game and its documents to a heritage institution or archive, which will take care of long-term preservation, whether or not the game has been released, and if the rights permit.
- "Deposit for archiving" does not mean "public access", still less "distribution". There are regulations protecting certain types of information, and it is possible to make agreements at the time of deposit.

More details

We recommend handing over the game and its documents to a heritage institution or archive, which will take care of long-term preservation, whether or not the game has been released, and if the rights permit.

We recommend transmitting the various documents in uncompressed files or with lossless compression, to guarantee file quality and avoid corrupting the original information.

At present, there are no institutions in Switzerland whose main mission is to collect and preserve video game heritage. However, some institutions are already able to preserve several types of material produced by a studio; for example, promotional material, or published paper or digital brochures. Other institutions already keep some video games in their collections, and are beginning to develop the necessary know-how to ensure their long-term preservation⁴.

You'll need to contact the institution most likely to be able to integrate a video game into its collections, depending on the profile of the institution or the region concerned:

- **National, cantonal, university and heritage libraries**

Switzerland's cantonal, university, public and heritage libraries have a wide range of missions, each focusing on a particular region or on one or more cultural, scientific or heritage fields. Libraries preserve all types of published works, and each has a specific mission to preserve and make available.

⁴This guide will be updated as progress is made in this area.

Some cantonal libraries have a legal deposit system, requiring the collection and preservation of any document, i.e. any book or brochure published or printed in their canton on any medium (including digital). All libraries, however, are at varying stages of progress in regard to the conservation of digital media.

- **Cantonal and municipal archives**

The mission of the cantonal and municipal archives is to collect, catalog and preserve all documents in unpublished form, such as manuscripts, maps and plans, contained in both administrative and private collections. Working documents, for example, can be integrated into the archive's holdings.

- **National and private museums**

Various museums, with national or private missions, have expressed or may express an interest in keeping video games in their collections. Some museums are also keen to show video games or other digital objects as part of their exhibitions.

With regard to the sensitivity of source code and other production information, it should be remembered that "deposit for archiving" does not mean "public access", still less "distribution". Strict conditions of access can be set at the time of deposit by an agreement signed by both parties, and the usual copyrights apply.

3.3 Costs and resources

In brief

- **We recommend that you consider the costs involved in documenting the game. This can be done by hiring a specialist consultant, or by implementing various internal measures to ensure this work is carried out.**

More details

Managing the documents and data produced during the creation of a video game involves various costs: documentation, storage, access and security, and preparation for archiving.

You can call on a consultant to help you with these questions.

It is also possible to implement various internal measures to ensure this work:

- Adoption of a documentation strategy.
- In a studio or group of creators, we recommend that each person be attentive to the documentation of his or her work. Nevertheless, one person can be designated to coordinate documentation efforts.

3.4 Archiving tools that can be useful to you

Depending on the level of requirement (and time) of each creator or studio, we recommend adapting some of the tools used by archivists, to make it easier to manage your game production.

3.4.1 Conservation schedule⁵

The conservation schedule is a tool for **estimating the conservation period of documents or data** produced by an entity. It lists the documents or data produced. It also specifies how long these documents must be kept, and what happens to them once this period has elapsed:

- Disposal
- conservation of part of the data (sample)
- Long-term preservation (archiving)

The aim is to target the various documents, data and information that are essential to retain.

3.4.2 Backup plan

A backup plan is applied to the various documents and data generated by an entity in the course of its activities. This plan makes it possible to determine upstream: **where and how these documents and data will be stored or preserved.**

We recommend always backing up documents and data generated using the "**3:2:1 method**", which requires 3 copies of documents and data, on 2 different media and in 1 different location.

- 3 data copies are made, if possible in different, open formats.
- 2 types of backups are performed on different media (hard disk, local server, etc.).
- 1 off-site backup is performed (on an external server, in the cloud, etc.).

⁵See for example https://www.vd.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/organisation/chancellerie/ACV/fichiers_pdf/dossier-thematique/Dossier-thematique-2011.pdf

3.4.3 Risk management plan⁶

This is an action plan prepared in advance by an entity, **enabling it to anticipate potential risks** (physical or digital) that could harm its activities.

- Documents and data essential to the smooth running of an entity's activities are listed.
- Risk types are defined and qualified.
- Measures to anticipate or mitigate the effects of these risks are also described.

A risk management plan is prepared along three lines:

1. **Risk prevention**
2. **Risk action plan**
3. **Repairing damage and getting back to business**

A risk management plan defines **three types of risk** according to their probability:

- Almost certain
- Possible
- Improbable

A risk management plan also makes it possible to define **several levels of risk severity**, depending on their impact on the entity's activities:

- Severe
- Very important
- Significant
- Moderate
- Insignificant

A risk management plan also makes it possible to estimate the **impact** these risks may have on an entity's activities:

- Extreme consequences
- Medium impact
- Low consequence

⁶See for example https://www.vd.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/organisation/chancellerie/ACV/fichiers_pdf/dossier-thematique/Dossier-thematique-2014.pdf

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<https://rapport.pixelvetica.ch>

5. Useful links

- Swiss Video Game Archivists (SVGA) website: <https://svga.ch/>
- SVGA's LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/svga-ch/>
- GameLab Lausanne (UNIL-EPFL), video game study group. See address: <https://gamelab-lausanne.ch/>

Appendices

A. Lexicon

Archiving⁷: "A set of actions designed to guarantee the long-term accessibility of information (files, documents, data) that must or wishes to be preserved for legal, historical or cultural reasons. It includes rules (procedures), skills and infrastructures."

Visual and sound assets: These are the resources created or used to design the game's graphics and sound universe (e.g. 3D models, textures, sound design elements, music, etc.).

Source code⁸ : "In computing, source code is a text that presents the instructions making up a program in readable form, as written in a programming language. Source code generally takes the form of a set of text files."

Administrative, project management and human resources documents: These are the documents that surround the production process, such as different types of contracts, financial documents, recruitment documents, game production monitoring documents, etc.

Game design documents: These are documents produced as part of the game system design process.

Narrative design documents: These are documents produced as part of the game's narrative and universe design.

Promotional documents: These are documents produced for the communication of the game (e.g. advertisements, posts on social networks, posters, etc.).

"Physical" documents: These are documents relating to the design of the game, and to the game in general, which are not in digital format (e.g. paper, prototypes in the form of board games, game boxes, merchandising, etc.).

⁷From: <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Archivage>, accessed April 16, 2025.

⁸From: https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Code_source, accessed April 16, 2025.

Rights: These are the legal "property" rights negotiated, granted (by contract) or guaranteed (by law) over a creation. These rights are made up of many aspects: intellectual property, commercial rights, usage rights, etc.

Format: Technical nature of an electronic document (e.g. .pdf, .csv, etc.).

Heritage or cultural institution: generally, publicly-funded entity (although private funding is also available) with one or more heritage missions to safeguard and make available.

Legal entity⁹ : "In law, a legal entity is an entity endowed with legal personality, which enables it to be the direct holder of rights and obligations in place of the natural or legal persons who make it up or who created them (e.g. companies, associations, etc.)".

Physical person¹⁰ : "A physical person is a legal term designating a human being who is recognized as having a legal personality, i.e. the capacity to exercise a certain number of rights and to take legal action".

Software tools: This refers to all the software tools used to create the game (e.g. programming libraries, game engine, Git or GitHub management tools, etc.).

⁹From: https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Personne_morale, accessed April 16, 2025.

¹⁰From: https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Personne_physique accessed April 16, 2025.

B. Tables

B.1 History of the studio

Creation date	<i>dd.mm.yyyy</i>
Date of cessation of activities	<i>dd.mm.yyyy</i>
Reason for cessation of activities	<i>Description of the context of cessation of activities</i>
Founding members	<i>First name Last name, First name Last name</i>
Active members	<i>First name Last name, First name Last name</i>
Types of positions held	<i>List of job types, titles, roles, etc. of individual members</i>
List of executives and key positions	<i>First name Last name of key studio personnel (if applicable and existing)</i>
Product list	<i>Game title + date</i>
List of co-produced games	<i>Game title + date + name of co-producer</i>
Head office or postal address	<i>Address, postal code, city, country (if several addresses, country to be indicated)</i>
Means of contact	<i>Telephone number, e-mail address, website, social network</i>

B.2 History of the game

Title	<i>Game name</i>
Created by	<i>Name of studio(s), author(s)</i>
Game license	<i>License name (e.g. GNU General Public License)</i>
Contributors	<i>Names of contributors</i>
Creation date	<i>dd.mm.yyyy</i>
Release date	<i>dd.mm.yyyy</i>
Game language(s)	<i>French, English, German, ...</i>
Funded by	<i>Name of entities</i>
Edited by	<i>Name of publishing company</i>
Distributed by	<i>Distributor company name</i>
Distribution method(s)	<i>Consoles, platforms, ...</i>
Game mode(s)	<i>Online, offline</i>
Game mode(s)	<i>Single-player, multiplayer</i>
Playing time	<i>Minutes, hours, ...</i>
Environment	<i>Media (computer, consoles), peripherals (mouse, keyboard, joysticks, etc.)</i>
Summary	<i>Game scenario, story summary</i>
Game type	<i>Game genre: e.g. deduction, simulation, action, etc.</i>
Preparatory material	<i>Sketches, storyboards, drawings, notes, emails...</i>
Promotional material	<i>Flyers, videos, interviews, press clippings, etc.</i>
Software used and versions	<i>Software + version</i>
File formats	<i>File types + formats</i>
Asset formats	<i>Asset types + formats</i>
Game version(s) available	<i>List of versions</i>
Available source code version(s)	<i>List of versions</i>

B.3 Rights management

Game license	<i>License name (e.g. GNU General Public License)</i>
Stakeholder(s) concerned by the contract	<i>List of stakeholders</i>
Stakeholder(s) owning the rights to the game	<i>List of stakeholders</i>
Distribution, exploitation and communication rights for the game	<i>List of rights and limitations</i>
Are there any exceptions to these rights?	<i>List of exemptions</i>
Contacting stakeholders affected by the contract	<i>Contact information for each stakeholder</i>
Contacting rights-holding stakeholders	<i>Contact information for each stakeholder</i>

B.4 Storage schedule

What types of documents/data are produced?	<i>List of documents/data produced</i>
What document/data formats are produced?	<i>List of formats for each document/product data</i>
What size data/documents are produced?	<i>Estimating the size of documents/data produced</i>
Where are data/documents stored?	<i>Lists of backup locations (servers, hard disks, etc.)</i>
How long are data/documents kept?	<i>Estimated retention period for each document</i>

B.5 Backup Plan

Copies made of documents/data produced	<i>List of copy formats</i>
Media on which documents/data are saved	<i>List of backup media (hard disks, servers, etc.)</i>
Off-site document/data storage locations	<i>List of backup locations (external server, cloud)</i>

B.6 Risk management

Type of risk	Probability	Gravity	Consequences
Theft or loss of equipment or back-up depot			
Backup hardware is corrupted			
Inability to retrieve documents or their latest version			
Unintentional deletion			
Departure of a person leading to the departure of certain data or information			
Lack of documentation on the context of creation			
Obsolescence of formats or software			
Non-possession of data			

B.7 Costs

Type of costs	Human costs	Financial costs	Space and time costs
Purchase of management and backup equipment			
Management and backup services			
Storage			
Operating			
External service provider			

C. Decision tree

D. Examples of game documentation

This guide accompanies the release of the report on the CQFD project - a video game archiving pilot project using DNA Studios' *Coronaquest* (2020) as a case study. We have chosen to use this game as an example of documentation.

Title	<i>CoronaQuest</i>
Created by	<i>DNA Studios</i>
Game license	<i>Not mentioned on public site CC-BY-NC-ND for archiving purposes</i>
Contributors	<i>Julien Schekter for the State of Vaud (sponsor) David Hofer and Martin Charrière for DNA Studios (design and development)</i>
Creation date	<i>29.04.2020</i>
Release date	<i>11.05.2020</i>
Game language(s)	<i>French, German, Italian, English, Spanish, Portuguese, Brazilian Portuguese, Albanian, Croatian, Serbian, Bosnian, Romanian</i>
Funded by	<i>State of Vaud, Department of Youth, Education and Culture</i>
Edited by	<i>No publisher</i>
Distributed by	<i>DNA Studios</i>
Distribution method(s)	<i>Web browser</i>
Game mode(s)	<i>Online</i>
Game mode(s)	<i>Solo</i>
Playing time	<i>Variable, 15 minutes on average</i>
Environment	<i>Computer</i>
Summary	<i>Description from the game's About page, dated 15.10.2024 "CoronaQuest is a video game developed in just a few days as part of the return to school on May 11, 2020 in the Canton of Vaud, Switzerland, to experience the start of a new school year in a more serene, secure climate and with a caring attitude towards one another. Its aim is</i>

	<p><i>to make you aware of the health measures and actions you can take to live together, at school and outside, with the coronavirus.</i></p> <p><i>During the period of confinement and in the current period, you are experiencing or have experienced funny, unique moments, boredom too and perhaps sadder days, but school has resumed, it continues, and all the professionals in the school environment are there to support you. This game will not only help you to consolidate your new habits, but we hope it will also give you a lot of fun and the opportunity to discuss this very special time together.</i></p> <p><i>Let's protect each other. Let's take care of each other.</i></p> <p><i>On August 18, 2020, the game is updated with a new league: the master league. Even more challenging, it includes new maps, some of which have even been proposed by students and classes from the Canton of Vaud!</i></p> <p><i>And welcome to CoronaQuest!"</i></p>
Game type	<i>Educational card game</i>
Preparatory material	<i>Emails, intermediate designs, source code Some documents have disappeared (card and effect design spreadsheet).</i>
Promotional material	<i>Educational sheet Communication on social networks</i>
Software used and versions	<i>Photoshop, unknown version PhpStorm, unknown version Matomo, unknown version Balsmiq, unknown version</i>
File formats	<i>PNG JPG AFDESIGN MP3</i>

	<i>For the code:</i> <i>TYPESCRIPT</i> <i>JSON</i> <i>JAVASCRIPT</i> <i>CSS</i> <i>BMPR</i>
Asset formats	<i>PNG</i> <i>AFDESIGN</i> <i>PSD</i> <i>MP3</i>
Game version(s) available	<i>August 18, 2020 version</i>
Available source code version(s)	<i>August 18, 2020 version</i>

E. Scale of documentation practices by profession

We suggest the following actions, which are not exhaustive, as each game may have its own particularities.

Business	Documents produced	Types of file formats	Backup actions to be taken	Intervention time (pre-, post-, production, etc.)	Benefits
Developer	Source code, "Read me" files	.md	Code hosting (e.g. on GitHub)	Production	Source codes can be reused for other projects
Artist	Concept art, assets	.jpg, .jpeg, .png, .tif, .tiff,	Saving art concepts and assets)	Pre-production and production	Concept art can be published in an artbook
Sound engineer	Audio files	.m4a, .mp3	Saving sound files	Production	Soundtracks can be published and sold independently of the game
Project Manager	Working documents, e-mails	.txt, .word, .pdf, .eml	Save all working documents needed to document the project	Pre-production, production and post-production	Useful for the next project or to publish a history of the game's production
HR Manager	Work documents, employee files, pay slips, e-mails	.txt, .word, .pdf, .eml	Confidential documents or documents	Pre-production, production and post-production	Keep track of all HR management, produce work certificates

			containing personal data must be handled in accordance with the Data Protection Act (DPA).		
Community manager	Publications on social networks, promotional videos, presentation texts	.html, .txt, .mp4, .mov, etc.	Archive the game's social network accounts (using Internet Archives, for example)	Pre-production, production, post-production	Managing and evaluating the communities surrounding a game is useful for producing statistics and understanding the audience.

Credits

Based on the work of:

Myriam Jouhar, *Archivage des jeux vidéo suisses : suivi et enjeux lors de la création d'un jeu vidéo (Lausanne 1830 : Histoires de registres, 2022)*, Genève: Haute école de gestion de Genève, 2022, 145 p.

Available at: <https://sonar.rero.ch/global/documents/323062>

Production: Myriam Jouhar, Aurore Lüscher (SVGA), Magalie Vetter (SVGA)

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